

REFORMS TO BE IMPLEMENTED IN THE PRESCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM AND PROSPECTIVE TASKS

Ibrokhimova Madina Ashurali kizi

2nd year student of majoring in preschool education,
Faculty of Pedagogy, University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences
Scientific supervisor: Akhmedova Madinabonu Makhmudjonovna
Acting associate professor at the Russian language department
University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10937636>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 3rd April 2024
Accepted: 4th April 2024
Published: 6th April 2024

KEYWORDS

*preschool education, reform,
adaptation, development, tasks.*

ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the reforms to be implemented in the preschool education system in Uzbekistan, as well as future tasks.

In the conditions of changes in the field of education, on the one hand, significant changes in all its areas, on the other hand, scientific and technical progress, changes in the nature and content of education, the development of an important and optimal strategy for the development of the field and a new approach and it is natural that it requires solutions. In this regard, there is also a need to analyze researches and predictions in the development of social views in society, relevant scientific researches, such analyzes can only be carried out based on scientific-critical and creative approaches, relying on deep knowledge and free thoughts. In the age of fast and information, everyday life, forms of interaction between people in society, everyone, especially pedagogues, need to make children understand that it is necessary not only to educate children, but also, first of all, to achieve high results and engage in social interaction, and to reveal their individual abilities. it is required to focus. Today, it is an urgent problem to provide the need for people who can actively and constructively solve the contradictions in various fields that exist in the society, have a creative approach, and the ability to initiate.

Since the end of 2017, the implementation of new fundamental reforms in the preschool education system, including the reconstruction, reconstruction, and perfect repair of preschool education systems, as well as the introduction of the public-private partnership system, resulted in a sharp increase in the coverage of children aged 3-7 years was raised. Priorities for the development of the preschool education system in 2024:

- ✓ Reconstruction of 27 kindergartens within the framework of the investment program, 20 at the expense of sponsorship funds, 11 at the expense of local budget funds, 5 public-private partnerships, establishment of 325 family kindergartens and preparation for school education. The percentage of coverage will be increased to 71.6% due to the establishment of additional 50 groups with a mandatory free system.
- ✓ In order to improve the quality of education, a system for evaluating the activities of kindergartens is introduced in the system, and their "Rating" is determined. In this case, the quality level is divided into "red", "yellow" and "green" regions. Errors and deficiencies in "red" regions will be monitored separately, and a financial incentive system will be introduced for pre-school education systems in "green" regions. In addition, a single methodical base for pedagogues and educators will be formed, and the activities of the regional "School of Skills" will be improved.
- ✓ Today, in order to provide children with healthy and safe food, a total of 149 state kindergartens in the region have established a service system using the "Outsourcing" method. In 2024 and subsequent years, the remaining public kindergartens will be gradually transferred to this system, and proposals will be submitted to the Republican Selection Commission.
- ✓ Today, non-state family kindergartens are established in 44 neighborhoods where there are no kindergartens. In this case, special control was taken on organization in remote, peripheral and low-coverage areas.

It is clear from the above that the most important tasks should be realistically implemented in the field of preschool education only in the period when the educational system is being renewed, that is, when education appears as a process that is consciously controlled and based

on special knowledge. It is necessary to pay attention to how the quality, content and direction of pre-school education and upbringing correspond to the requirements of the time, and to eliminate the shortcomings in this regard quickly.

At present, it is noticeable that there are cases of unclear perception of childhood and children's world by adults, and at the same time, who is a child today, what is his purpose, what is the essence of development, who should he be and what kind of education should he receive, it is very difficult to get reasonable answers to the questions. Based on this, in our opinion, despite the fact that there are enough deep ideas about many aspects of human nature in the fields of scientific knowledge such as philosophy, psychology, sociology, pedagogy, these sciences are not correct in the laws of modern human development. It is noticeable that they do not have the necessary knowledge, especially in the development of preschool children, and in turn, it increases the importance of analyzing the specific characteristics of the development of preschool children.

The existence of different views on the specific characteristics of the development of preschool children, in our opinion, leads to a lack of clear understanding of the purpose of the activities of the preschool stage, which is the foundation of the educational system. Even today, within the scope of sociology, the essence and meaning of this activity:

- ❖ as a stage of preparing children for school;
- ❖ as the first steps in the development of the child's personality;
- ❖ there are different views as the period of formation of the main mechanisms and ways of effective adaptation of the child to the society.

Through the reforms implemented in preschool education, existing problems have been pedagogically researched taking into account the possibilities of the system, perspectives of a modern approach to education of preschool children have been developed. And now it is done by studying the specific features of the role and tasks of the preschool education organization in the child's life based on general theoretical and sociological approaches, pedagogical understanding of the problems of preschool children, psychological support for the development of the child's personality, preschool education for the child. social and personal direction in his life, the leading types of activity of a preschool education organization pedagogue-educator, the study of the existing problems in it directly opens the way to solving the problems of the preschool education system. At the same time, the sociological analysis of the important features of the current state of the preschool education system in our country, which is striving for development, is important in determining the level of further improvement of this field.

In today's renewed Uzbekistan, it is important to work based on modern ideas and concepts, educational requirements based on the child's personality, based on new educational programs, based on the theory of personality, activity and social structure, in accordance with the current requirements of preschool children is earning. From a content point of view, the process of children's development allows us to get acquainted with the above-mentioned values, norms, knowledge, forms of behavior, attitude to everyone as a certain culture, and the process of socialization. From this point of view, even in the reforms of the preschool education system today, the child's socialization and quality education are considered as the main factors. Relying on this factor, the issues of education and upbringing of children of preschool age are also of particular importance. The purpose of this is to establish a system of preschool

education based on modern requirements. In this regard, the fact that our state has provided material support for the industry deserves recognition. The next step is to raise the quality of education for children of preschool age to a new level. It is not an exaggeration to say that the destiny and development of the nation always begins with the education of the preschool child, and the development of the child's mind, thinking, and behavior towards life and society. doesn't. We should educate our children in such a way that they can have their own self and be able to socialize quickly in society.

In conclusion, we should say that there are more important priorities that we need to do in the preschool education system. Further improvement of the pre-school education system, expansion of the network of pre-school education organizations and strengthening of the material and technical base, providing them with qualified pedagogic personnel, modern educational programs for the all-round intellectual, spiritual-aesthetic and physical development of children and Our main goal is to introduce technologies in the educational process, to radically increase their level of preparation for school. Because our tomorrow and our future depend on our little children who are growing up and being educated in preschool education organizations today. Our honorable president said, "The future and well-being of our country depends on how our children grow up to be human beings. Our main task is to create the necessary conditions for young people to show their potential"- his words place great trust and responsibility on our leaders. He calls each of us to be more patriotic. Therefore, let's not be indifferent to the fate of our children, who are the future of our country.

REFERENCES:

1. Solieva, Z. B., & Javburieva, R. USE OF GAMES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. *УЧЕНЫЙ XXI ВЕКА*, 18.
2. Солиева, З. Б. ПРОБЛЕМА ЛЕКСИКОГРАФИЧЕСКОЙ ОБРАБОТКИ СЛОВА И СПОСОБЫ ЕЕ РЕШЕНИЯ. *УЧЕНЫЙ XXI ВЕКА*, 27.
3. Eshmatova, Y. (2022). Анализ человеческой психики в повестях. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz)*, 23(23).
4. Эшматова, Ю. (2022). ПРОБЛЕМЫ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО ПСИХОЛОГИЗМА В УЗБЕКСКОМ ЛИТЕРАТУРОВЕДЕНИИ. *ТА'ЛИМ VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMYI JURNALI*, 2(11), 155-161.
5. Воумахматовна, Е. У. (2022). WRITER'S SKILL AND LANDSCAPE IMAGE. *ТА'ЛИМ VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMYI JURNALI*, 2(11), 143-146.
6. Eshmatova, Y. (2022). О 'ZGA TILLI GURUHLARDA SHE'RLARNING JANR XUSUSIYATLARINI FARQLASHGA О 'RGATISH. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz)*, 23(23).
7. Eshmatova, Y. (2022). ЎЗБЕК АЁЛИ РУҲИАТИНИНГ ЁРИТИЛИШИДА ЯНГИ ҚИРРАЛАРНИНГ НАМОЁН БЎЛИШИ. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz)*, 23(23).
8. МАМАТҚУЛОВ, В. (2024). О 'ZBEKISTON JANUBIY VILOYATLARIDA SANOAT KORXONALARINING TASHKIL ETILISHI VA HUDUDLAR SANOATINING IXTISOSLASHUVI JARAYONINING TARIXIY TAHLILI (1930-1950 yy). *News of UzMU journal*, 1(1.2. 1).

9. Sherozovich, M. B. (2024). INDUSTRIAL MEASURES IN UZBEKISTAN 1925-1954 AND THEIR RESULTS (in the case of Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions). *World scientific research journal*, 24(1), 195-200.
10. Sherozovich, M. B., & Shuhratovna, M. N. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF FOOD INDUSTRIES IN THE SOUTHERN REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN: HISTORICAL ANALYSIS AND CONSEQUENCES. *World scientific research journal*, 24(1), 188-194.
11. Sherozovich, M. B. (2024). CONFLICT SITUATIONS IN THE PROCESS OF TRAINING INDUSTRY PERSONNEL IN SURKHANDARYA AND KASHKADARYA REGIONS: HISTORICAL ANALYSIS AND RESULTS (1925-1950). *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 39(5), 221-225.
12. Sherozovich, M. B., & Shuhratovna, M. N. (2024). THE EMERGENCE OF THE GAS-SULFUR INDUSTRY IN UZBEKISTAN AND ITS DEVELOPMENT HISTORY (IN THE EXAMPLE OF KASHKADARYA REGION). *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 39(5), 217-220.
13. Rustamkulovna, S. T. (2022). SOCIAL FACTORS OF ETHNOCULTURAL TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(4), 622-626.
14. Сафарова, Т. Р. (2022). ЗАМОНАВИЙ ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМ ТИЗИМИДА ФАЛСАФАНИ ЎҚИТИШНИНГ ВАЗИФАЛАРИ ВА МУАММОЛАРИ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(9), 657-664.
15. Сафарова, Т. Р. (2021). ВЛИЯНИЕ ПАНДЕМИИ COVID-19 НА СОСТОЯНИЕ ЭТНОКУЛЬТУРНОГО ТУРИЗМА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. In *Новые вызовы новой науки: опыт теоретического и эмпирического анализа* (pp. 176-183).
16. Kholdarova, F. (2017). SOME ASPECTS OF NATIONAL PECULIARITIES IN POLITICAL NEGOTIATIONS. In *Перспективы развития научных исследований в 21 веке* (pp. 149-150).
17. Kholdarova, F. (2017). SOME ASPECTS OF NATIONAL PECULIARITIES IN POLITICAL NEGOTIATIONS. In *Перспективы развития научных исследований в 21 веке* (pp. 149-150).
18. Холдарова, Ф. Т. (2018). Стратегия повышения эффективности политических переговоров Узбекистана в регионе Центральной Азии. In *Theory and practice of scientific research* (pp. 268-270).
19. Ugli, I. J. T., Tuxtabayevna, K. F., & Ugli, I. S. T. (2020). Comparison of Similes and Metaphors in Translations (In Act of Beneficent Knowledge). *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(05).
20. Очилова, Г. А., Жумаева, Ш. С., & Курбонова, М. Б. (2019). Политика межнациональных отношений и толерантность в Узбекистане. *Наука, образование и культура*, (9 (43)), 15-18.
21. Жумаева, Ш. С., & Очилова, Г. А. (2019). ТВОРЧЕСКАЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ И ЕЁ ГУМАНИСТИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ. *Научное знание современности*, (2), 5-10.
22. Навои, А. (2016). Проблема этических норм развития науки в трудах мыслителей средневековой Средней Азии. *Молодой учёный*, 6, 670.
23. Жумаева, Ш. С. (2023). АХБОРОТ ХАВФСИЗЛИГИ ВА МАФКУРАВИЙ ҲИМОЯ. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(5 SPECIAL), 286-290.

24. Suyunovna, J. S. (2023). The Culture of Reading as a Phenomenon of Spiritual Life. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(5), 84-87.
25. Taxirovna, A. S. LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS IN THE TRANSLATION OF STORIES BETWEEN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS, 2023/2/c12.
26. Taxirovna, A. S. (2024). COLLABORATIVE LEARNING: FOCUSING ON TECHNIQUES THAT PROMOTE TEAMWORK AND SHARED KNOWLEDGE AMONG STUDENTS, SO 'NGI ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR NAZARIYASI.
27. Taxirovna, A. S. (2023). Lingua-cultural aspects of the translation of English and Uzbek stories, *Current Issues of Bio Economics and Digitalization in the Sustainable Development of Regions (Germany)*.
28. Mamatkulov, B. (2021). Conflicts of the process of the industrial staff training in the soviet period. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(10), 507-510.
29. Mamatkulov, B. (2021, November). A New Interpretation of Industry in Uzbekistan During Independence. In " *ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM* (pp. 158-161).
30. Маматкулов, Б. (2023). О 'ZBEKISTONDA GAZ-OLTINGUGURT SANOATINING YUZAGA KELISHI VA UNING RIVOJLANISH TARIXI (QASHQADARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA). *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences.*, 3(12/1).
31. Suyunovna, J. S. (2023). Combination of Mythological, Religious and Philosophical Worldviews.
32. Алиева, З. Р. (2020). Роль дистанционного обучения в методике преподавания русского языка как иностранного. *Молодой ученый*, (35), 176-178.
33. Алиева, З. Р. (2024). ТЕОРИЯ РЕЧЕВОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В КОНТЕКСТЕ ПСИХОЛИНГВИСТИКИ. *SCHOLAR*, 2(5), 121-126.
34. Kakharova, D. S. (2020). CREATIVITY OF THE FUTURE TEACHER. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University*, 4(2), 337-342.
35. Кахарова, Д. С. БЎЛАЖАК ЎҚИТУВЧИНИНГ ИЖОДИЙ ИМКОНИАТЛАРИ ТВОРЧЕСКИЙ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ БУДУЩЕГО УЧИТЕЛЯ CREATIVITY OF THE FUTURE TEACHER Саидова Гулрух Ҳалим қизи.
36. Ахмедов, О. С. (2010). Лексико-семантические проблемы при переводе с английского языка налоговых и таможенных терминов. *Филологические науки. Вопросы теории и практики*, (1-2), 18-21.
37. Ахмедов, О. С. (2014). Калькирование в налоговой и таможенной терминосистеме узбекского языка. *Вестник Челябинского государственного университета*, (3 (332)), 12-15.